

THE SEMANTIC FEATURES OF THE TERMS IN THE FIELD OF REAL ESTATE ACTIVITY

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Abstract: This article is devoted to analyze the semantic features of the terms in the field of realtor in English and Uzbek languages.

Key words: economic terms, terminology, terminological system, a non-term, affiliation, real estate agent

Today we are witnessing the process of globalization in all aspects of human life: economy, politics and culture. Globalization in the economic sphere is manifested in the continuous interaction and integration of national economic systems, which is the result of the growth of international trade, investments and capital movements. Globalization implies the formation of a single international economic space in which information, goods, services and real estate activities can flow freely. This means that the globalization of economic processes always requires the process of internationalization of the terminological apparatus of economics. After all, the essence of this process is the unification of economic terminology and the emergence of an international version of economic terms. Here, it is worth noting that the source of internationalism, as a rule, is the language of international communication, which is English today.

This article is devoted to a comparative analysis of the performance of equivalents of economic terms in their languages in order to determine the coverage of international terms in a specific field terminological system, including the role of international terms in real estate activity. In order to fulfill this task, the content of real estate terminology in English and Uzbek languages was analyzed at the linguistic level, and in order to systematize its conceptual apparatus, it was necessary to first consider the term and terminology research.

There are many comments about the definition of the term in the scientific literature. In almost all definitions, the term is described as a word or phrase expressing a special scientific and technical concept.

According to O. Vinokur, the term is always clear and obvious. The language of the system of terms is formed consciously¹. After all, the term does not appear by itself, spontaneously, but is created due to its necessity, the existence of a need for it in society. According to A.S. Gerd, a term is a natural and artificial language unit, that is, a word or a combination of words, with a

¹ Винокур Г.О. О некоторых явлениях словообразования в русской технической терминологии. Труды МИФЛИ. Т. Сборник статей по языкознанию. - М., 1961.-С.3-10.

special terminological meaning that clearly and completely reflects the main features of existing concepts at a certain stage of the development of science². O.S. Akhmanova says that terminology emerges only when a science reaches the highest level of its development, that is, the term is recognized after a specific concept acquires a clear scientific expression. An important means of distinguishing a term from a non-term is that it cannot be scientifically defined³.

In linguistics, the concept of terminology is the basis of a general theory and is interpreted as a science that studies the collection, definition, formation and presentation of lexical units related to a special field in one or more languages. According to the explanation given by H. Felber, who conducted research in this field, the interpretation of the concept of terminology has three different definitions: "1) it is an interdisciplinary science that studies terms that express a special concept; 2) a set of terms representing a system of concepts related to a special field; 3) is the promotion of special field concepts expressed by terms"⁴. The main object of terminology is the term, therefore, the need for interpretation of the concept of the term becomes important.

A. V. Mayitova, in her dissertation, which researched banking work from a linguistic-cognitive aspect, mentions the existence of the following methods of term formation noted by world linguists in their scientific works:

- 1) semantic method (using a common word or phrase as a term with a new meaning;
- 2) morphological method (formation of a new term by adding affixes and words to each other);
- 3) syntactic method (formation of terminological phrases);
- 4) acquisition of words and phrases:
 - a) from universal lexicon and other terminological systems;
 - b) from other languages (acquisitions)⁵.

It is known that the classification of field terms into thematic groups on the basis of their integral and differential features in the terminology research makes it possible to define more precisely the limits of their scope of use. Based on this approach, the criteria for dividing the terms into several large and small thematic groups based on the structural and semantic characteristics of the

² Герд А.С. Значение термина и научное знание//Научнотехническая информация. Серия 2.-М.,1991. №10.- С.1-4.

³ Ахманова О.С.,Тер-Мкртчян С.А. Научное определение как лингвистическая и семиотическая проблема. Проблематика определений терминов в словарях разных типов.-М.: Наука, 1976.-С.57- 63.

⁴ Felber H. Terminological work and standardization of terminology. – Paris, 1974. p.1

⁵ Майтлова А.В.Терминосистема предметно специального языка —банковское дело|| в лингвокогнитивном аспекте: дисс... канд.филол.наук. – Саратов, 2008. – С.24.

terms related to the field of real estate and the scope of their use were developed:

1. **The criterion of formal affiliation** is to unite the terms that have a formal commonality, that is, that have a common component in the structure, into one thematic group.

2. **Criterion of semantic affiliation** - combining terms that do not have a formal commonality, i.e., do not have the same component in their structure, into one thematic group based on their common semantic structure.

It should be noted that in both English and Uzbek terms related to the field of real estate can be grouped based on both criteria. For example, the presence of the real estate component in English terms such as **real** estate agent, **real** estate broker, **real** estate office, **real** estate developer clearly indicates that they belong to the thematic group of real estate.

Similarly, in the Uzbek language, the common term in terms of real estate **rieltorlik** faoliyati, **rieltorlik** tashkiloti, **rieltorlik** xizmatlari, **rieltorlik** tashkiloti litsenziyasi is based on this, we classify these terms into the group of semantic affiliation criteria.

However, the English terms **rieltor** and **real estate agent** do not have a formal commonality, so they are grouped according to the second criterion.

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